

Environmental Contamination with Geohelminths Eggs in Ifetedo, South-western Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT:

The study assessed the prevalence, types and abundance of geohelminth eggs in the soil of the study area. The study involved soil examination for infective stages of geohelminth parasites. Five public primary schools were randomly selected for the study and topsoil samples were collected from the playgrounds, near the classroom, and around the toilets of each school to determine the type and number of infective geohelminth agents using sucrose floatation techniques. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to summarize helminth eggs distribution according to ecological sites of soil collection. Out of 90 soil samples collected around toilets, near classrooms and playgrounds in the five schools examined, helminth eggs were identified from 21(23.3%). The rate of contamination was highest near toilets (47.6%) and lowest near the classrooms (19%). Mean egg count/g of soil was also revealed highest near toilets (7.03 ± 1.07) and lowest at playgrounds (4.14 ± 3.59). The study concluded that soil contamination is the important risk factors in the transmission of soil-transmitted helminthiasis in the study area

KEYWORDS: Contamination, Geohelminth, Helminthiasis, Ifetedo and Osun.

INTRODUCTION

The soil-transmitted helminths are nematodes commonly known as intestinal worms. They include roundworms (e.g. *Ascaris lumbricoides*), whipworm (e.g. *Trichuris trichiura*), threadworm (e.g. *Strongyloides stercoralis*) and hookworms (e.g. *Ancylostoma duodenale* and *Necator americanus*) [5]. They are most common in regions exhibiting warm and moist climates coupled with poor sanitation and hygiene. Soil-transmitted helminths have an impact on human health and the socio-economic conditions of affected communities. Epidemiologically, it is well established that though individuals of all age's harbour worms, the highest rates occur among children in rural areas of the tropical and subtropical areas [4]. Human lifestyle and behaviours have been implicated to exacerbate transmission of soil-transmitted helminths. Predominant among these are poverty, inadequate sanitation, lack of access to health care, and overcrowding [13]. Besides, barefooting and eating unwashed fruits and vegetables are also vital risk factors. These predisposing factors point to school-age children as the most vulnerable group with the highest risk of STH infection. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that almost two billion people are infected with one or more soil-transmitted helminths, mainly *Ascaris lumbricoides*, hookworm, and *Trichuris trichiura*. School-aged children have been shown to be the population at greatest risk of acquiring infections with roundworm, hookworm, and whipworm infections [14]. The existence of viable geohelminth eggs in the superficial layer of soil presents a potential public health hazard, especially that these eggs are extremely resistant to adverse weather and chemical agents. Thus, soil contamination seems to be the most direct indicator of the risk of STH infection among the human population. For this reason, many studies have been carried out in recent years to determine the prevalence of geohelminth eggs in the soil of parks, playgrounds, sand pits, beaches, backyards and gardens, farmyard and other urban and rural areas. Soil

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contamination with helminth eggs has been reported in different countries worldwide [2], [9]. In Nigeria, studies on the evaluation of soil-transmitted helminths (STH) eggs contamination of the environment in different localities include those of Maikai *et al.* [11] who noted prevalence rate of 62% of helminths in Kaduna, Nigeria and Sam-Wobo *et al.* [14] who reported prevalence levels of 17.8 to 87% in various communities in Ogun State, Nigeria, which was ascribed to the high biotic potential of the worm as well as the ability of eggs to withstand adverse conditions. Unfortunately, there is a paucity of information on the contamination of soil with helminth eggs in the study area. Thus, the objective of this study was to analyze soil samples collected from schools surroundings in order to assess the types and abundance of helminth species in the soil of the study area and to devise effective control strategy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area

This study was conducted in Ifetedo, Ife South Local Government Area of Osun State in south-western Nigeria. Ifetedo lies between Latitudes 7°10'21"N and 7°11'14"N and Longitudes 004°41'25"E and 004°42'50"E. It is located on an elevation of 217 meters above sea level. The climate of the area is typically tropical with a characteristic dry season of about six months (October-March) and a wet season of about 6 months (April- September) [1]. The average annual rainfall is over 2000mm. The mean temperature is 27°C and annual range temperature range is 2-3°C. The mean relative humidity is over five per cent and high relative humidity above 90 % [6]. The vegetation of the area is tropical rainforest, characterized by large and tall trees. The inhabitants are predominantly Yoruba speaking people of the Southwest with a mixture of people from different ethnic groups in Nigeria.

Sample collection and analysis

Duplicate topsoil samples were taken from three ecologically relevant spots in the school. These were the playground, near classrooms and around the toilets. Samples were kept in polythene bags, tied, and well labelled with the date of collection. The samples were taken to the laboratory for the analysis of the presence and number of helminth eggs or larvae.

Twenty grams (20g) of soil sample was suspended in 50ml of 0.1% tween 80 solution, mixed with a magnetic stirrer. The resulting mixture was sieved through a 400µm mesh size and the filtrate centrifuged at 3000rpm for 10mins. The supernatant was discarded and the sediment further suspended in 5ml of prepared sucrose solution (specific gravity 1.3), centrifuged at 1000 rpm for another 10mins. The supernatant was transferred to a 10ml tube by Pasteur pipette, dilute with floating solution up to 7ml and again centrifuged at 1000rpm for 5mins. After this, the tube was filled to the brim with sucrose (floating solution) and covered with a coverslip. About thirty minutes later, the coverslip was removed, placed onto a glass slide and examined under a compound microscope at X10 and X40 magnifications. The numbers of helminth eggs in the whole slide were counted.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Statistical analysis of data was done using a descriptive method on the SPSS-23 platform. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize helminth eggs distribution according to ecological sites of soil collection.

RESULTS

Out of 90 soil samples collected around toilets, classrooms and playgrounds in five schools examined by this study, helminth eggs were identified from 21 or 23.3% (Table 1). The rate of contamination was highest near toilets (10 of 21 sites or 47.6%) and lowest near the classrooms (4 of 21 or 19%).

The three helminth species recovered from the soil sample were *A. lumbricoides*, *T. trichiura* and hookworms with predominant parasites of *A. lumbricoides*.

The rate of soil contamination was highest in school 5 with a prevalence of 38.9 %; the lowest contamination was recorded in School 2, School 3 and School 4 all with a prevalence of 16.7%.

The mean egg intensity varied from 0.0 eggs per gram (epg) of soil at the playground in school 4, near the classroom at school 2, and near the classroom at school 5 to 9.0 eggs/g of soil near classrooms at the School 1. Statistical analysis showed that this pattern of variation was different; school 1 has the highest epg of soil with 8.40 ± 0.40 epg while School 4 has the lowest epg of 3.64 ± 2.58 . (Table 1).

Mean intensity of egg by location examined shows that soil samples from near toilets have the highest intensity of 7.03 ± 1.07 , followed by playgrounds with 5.00 ± 2.87 epg while lowest mean intensity was observed in samples taken from near classroom with 4.14 ± 3.59 .(Table 1)

The highest number of geohelminth eggs in soil was detected in near toilet (1,516) and lowest near classroom (519). Table 1 and 2 shows the number of isolated soil-transmitted helminth species from the soil samples. *Ascaris lumbricoides* had the highest occurrence in the contaminated samples 1,396 (49 %), followed by Hookworms 883 (31%) while the least abundance was *T.trichiura* of 569 (23%).

Table 1: Egg intensity distribution according to schools and sites of investigation

Schools	Stations	No of samples	No of samples with eggs (%)	Total no of eggs detected	No of eggs(range)/20g of soil	Mean \pm SD egg/g of soil
School 1	Near toilet	6	3(50)	470	157(129-176)	8.00 \pm 1.00
	Near classroom	6	1(16.7)	180	180(180-180)	9.00 \pm 0.00
	Playground	6	1(16.7)	162	162(162-162)	8.10 \pm 0.00
School 2	Near toilet	18	5(27.8)	812	162(129-180)	8.40 \pm 0.40
	Near classroom	6	1(16.7)	142	142(142-142)	7.10 \pm 0.00
	Playground	6	0(0)	0	0(0)	0.00 \pm 0.00
School 3	Near toilet	6	2(33.3)	296	148(135-161)	7.40 \pm 0.65
	Near classroom	6	3(16.7)	438	146(135-161)	4.83 \pm 3.42
	Playground	18	1(16.7)	120	120(120-120)	6.00 \pm 0.00
School 4	Near toilet	6	1(16.7)	128	128(128-128)	6.40 \pm 0.00
	Near classroom	6	1(16.7)	108	108(108-108)	5.40 \pm 0.00
	Playground	18	3(16.7)	356	119(108-128)	5.90 \pm 0.41
School 5	Near toilet	6	1(16.7)	113	113(113-113)	5.65 \pm 0.00
	Near classroom	6	2(33.3)	211	106(96-115)	5.28 \pm 0.38
	Playground	6	0(0)	0	0(0)	0.00 \pm 0.00
Total	Near toilet	18	3(16.7)	324	108(96-115)	3.64 \pm 2.58
	Near classroom	6	4(66.7)	671	68(91-205)	8.39 \pm 2.26
	Playground	6	0(0)	0	0(0)	0.00 \pm 0.00
Total	Near toilet	6	3(50)	247	82(52-107)	4.12 \pm 1.14
	Near classroom	18	7(38.9)	918	131(52-205)	4.17 \pm 3.43
	Playground	30	10(33.3)	1,516	151(91-205)	7.03 \pm 1.07
Total	Near classroom	30	4(13.4)	519	130(96-180)	4.14 \pm 3.59
	Playground	30	7(23.3)	813	16(52-161)	5.00 \pm 2.87
		90	21(23.3)	2,848	136(52-205)	5.39 \pm 1.21

Table 2: Egg distribution according to species of geohelminths encountered

Schools	Examined sites	Total No of eggs detected	Numbers of eggs (%)		
			Ascaris	Hookworms	<i>T.trichiura</i>
School 1	Near toilet	470	174(37)	216(46)	80(17)
	Near classroom	180	109(61)	43(24)	28(15)
	Playground	162	87(53.7)	75(46.3)	0(0)
		812	370(45.6)	334(41)	108(13.3)
School 2	Near toilet	142	142(100)	0(0)	0(0)
	Near classroom	0	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Playground	296	122(41.2)	68(23)	106(35.8)
		438	210(48)	68(15.5)	160(36.5)
School 3	Near toilet	120	72(60)	41(34.2)	7(5.8)
	Near classroom	128	55(45.8)	38(31.7)	35(29.2)
	Playground	108	108(100)	0(0)	0(0)
		356	235(66)	79(22.2)	42(11.8)
School 4					

	Near toilet	113	99(87.6)	14(12.4)	0(0)
	Near classroom	211	0(0)	211(100)	0(0)
	Playground	0	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
		324	99(31)	225(69)	0(0)
School 5					
	Near toilet	671	235(35)	177(26.4)	259(38.6)
	Near classroom	0	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)
	Playground	247	247(100)	0(0)	0(0)
		918	482(52.5)	177(19.3)	259(28.2)
Total					
	Near toilet	1,516	794(52.4)	448(30)	346(22.8)
	Near classroom	519	252(48.6)	292(56.3)	63(12)
	Playground	813	564(69.4)		106(13)
				143(17.6)	
		2,848	1,396(49)	883(31)	569(23)

DISCUSSION

The rate of soil contamination in the school compounds was found to be 23.3%. The overall result was similar to the findings of Cassenote, *et al.*, [9] and Ntonifor *et al.*, [12] but lower than that reported by Horiuchi *et al.*, [13].

The contamination might have resulted from open defecation, rain splashes, irrigation or river flush of contaminated soil during heavy rainfall which deposit contaminated soil on the surface of leaves of vegetables [15]. It is also possible that the soil moisture must have favoured contamination of the areas and the survival of the parasites.

The three helminth species recovered from the soil sample were *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *T.trichiura* and hookworms with predominant numbers of *A. lumbricoides*. *A. lumbricoides* eggs are resistant to harsh environmental conditions which may account for the ubiquitous nature of egg distributions and hence high abundance in soil. The results obtained in the present studies also showed that geohelminth ova and larvae are commonly found in all school environments in Ifetedo Osun State, South-west of Nigeria. The detection of helminthic ova/ larvae in the school surroundings has a significant public health implication to pupils who have close contact with the soil [16]. This is of great importance in the health of many populations in developing countries where illiteracy, poverty and associated poor environmental sanitation practices have been implicated in the heavy burden of helminthiasis [17].

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that *A. lumbricoides* were most abundant helminth species contaminating the soil of the study area. The presence of helminth eggs in the soil may cause high prevalence of Soil-transmitted helminths infections among the school children if sanitation is inadequate. This research provides information on types of geo-helminth species involved in the environmental contamination of the study area. The study has implications for public health control and environmental management. The findings, therefore, provide useful information that will help policy makers, particularly the federal and states ministries of health plan effective and sustainable STH control programmes in the study area and similar communities.

REFERENCES:

- [1]. Drake, L., Jukes M., Sternberg, R. J and Bundy, D.A.P (2010). Geo-Helminthiasis (Ascariasis, Trichuriasis and Hookworm): Cognitive and Development Impact. Seminars in paediatric Infectious Diseases 11(4): 245-251.
- [2]. Bethony, J., Brooker, S., Albonico, M., Geiger, A.L., Diemert, D. and Hotez, P.J. (2006). Soil Transmitted Helminth Infections: Ascariasis, Trichuriasis and Hookworm. Lancet 367, 1521-1532.
- [3]. WHO (2002). Prevention and Control of Schistosomiasis and Soil transmitted Helminthiasis: Report of a WHO Expert Committee. World Health Organization Technical Report Series, vol. 912, pp. 2-5.
- [4]. WHO (2016). Soil Transmitted Helminths whofactsheet.htm.

- [5]. Alonso, J. M., Stein, M., Chamorro, M. C. and Bojanich, M. V. (2001). Contamination of Soil with Eggs of *Toxocara* in a Subtropical City in Argentina. *Journal of Helminthology*, 75: 165 – 168.
- [6]. Mizgajska, H., (2001). Soil Contamination with *Toxocara* Spp. Eggs in the Krakow Area and Two near by Villages. *Transaction of Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene*, 46: 105 – 190.
- [7]. Akinbuwa, O. and Adeniyi, I. F. (1996). Seasonal Variation, Distribution and Inter Relationships Rotifers in Opa Reservoir, Nigeria. *African Journal of Ecology*, 34:351-365.
- [8]. Iwena, O. A. (2012). *Essential Geography Sixth Edition*. pp. 426 Tonad Publishers Limited.
- [9]. Cassenote, A. J., Pinto-Neto, J. M. and Ferriera, A.W. (2014). Soil Contamination By Eggs of Soil-Transmitted Helminths With Zoonotic Potential in The Town of Fernandopolis, State of Sao Paulo Brazil, Between 2007 and 2008. *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicinal Tropical*. 44(3):371-374.
- [10]. Magnaval, J. F., Glickman, I. T., Dorchie, p., Morassin, B. (2001). Highlights of Human Toxocariasis. *Korean Journal of Parasitology*, 39: 1 – 11.
- [11]. Maikai, B. V., Umoh, J. U., Ajanusi, O. J., and Ajogi, I. (2008). Public Health Implications of Soil Contaminated with Helminth Eggs in the Metropolis of Kaduna, Nigeria. *Journal of Helminthology*, 82: 113-118.
- [12]. Ntonifor, N. G, Irene, N. S and Tabot, J. E. (2016). Soil-Transmitted Helminth Infections and Associated Risk Factors in a Neglected Region in the Upper Nkongho-mbo Area, South-west Region, Cameroon. *International Journal of Tropical Disease and Health*, 16(3): 1-9.
- [13]. Horiuchi, S., Paller, V .G, Uga S. (2013). Soil Contamination by Parasite Eggs in a Rural Village in the Philippines. *Tropical Biomedicine*, 30(3):495-503.
- [14]. Sam-Wobo, S.O., Mafiana, C.F., and Idowu, A.B. (2014). The Effects of Surface Soil Exchangeable Cations on the Prevalence of *Ascaris lumbricoides* in Ogun state, Nigeria. *The Nigerian Society for Parasitology*, 25:25-31.
- [15]. Agbolade, O. M., Akinboye, D. O., Fajebe, O. T., Abolade, O. A. and Adebambo, A. A. *Tropical Biomedical*, 2008, 21:15-22.
- [16]. Bethony, J., Brooker, S., Albonico, M., Geiger, S. M., Loukas, A., Diemert, D. and Hotez, P. J. *Lancet*, 2006, 36 (19521): 1521- 1532.
- [17] Wagbatsoma, U. A. and Aisien, M. B. *Nigeria Journal of Parasitology*, 2000, 113: 87-95.

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